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Investigating The Lexical Concept of “War” & “Conflict” Concerning Israel vs Palestine in BBC 2023

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Abstract

The article analyzed the lexical concept of war and conflict as a noun in the news coverage of Israel vs Palestine on BBC Channel 2023. The study employed a qualitative methods, utilizing a corpus-based approach. The researchers acquired data from 25 news articles regarding Israel vs Palestine on BBC Channel 2023. The goal of the study was to identify instances of “war” and “conflict” as nouns by examining the differences in lexical concepts associated with each term. The lexical concept is constructed based on the contextual elements that influence it. Moreover, it was found that the frequency of the words "war" and "conflict" as nouns in BBC Channel 2023 varied greatly. The study demonstrated the cognitive linguistic relationship between “war” and “conflict”, revealing the interconnection due to the ongoing a backdrop of the battle that continues to the present day. The two lexical concepts derived from both nouns are event and action.

Keywords: Lexical Concept, Cognitive Linguistic, War, Conflict, Corpus-Based Approach

1. Introduction

The Israel-Palestine conflict has persisted since 1917, when the Balfour Declaration was issued. The Balfour Declaration, in essence, is a campaign intended to advocate for the creation of a Jewish nation in Palestine, a region that holds historical significance as the Land of Israel. Israel has engaged in protracted military offensives against Gaza in 2008, 2012, 2014, 2021, 2023, and 2024, stemming from a long-standing conflict spanning centuries. The protracted struggle is mostly attributed to three factors: (1) The advent of the Zionist movement, (2) Discontentment with the Balfour Declaration, and (3) Discontentment with the proposal to partition Palestine. (BBC, 2023).

The Israeli assault has garnered significant media coverage, especially from the online platform of the BBC (British Broadcasting Corporation). Typically, the internet media content of the BBC (British Broadcasting Corporation) originates from the United Kingdom, indicating its endorsement of Israel. England endorses the concept of a sovereign Palestine that can coexist alongside the state of Israel. The global community is closely monitoring the ongoing Israeli military operations in Gaza, Palestine, which persist to this day in 2024. Researchers

are interested in examining the lexical concept of war and conflict as nouns in the news coverage of Israel vs Palestine on the BBC channel in 2023.

This study employs cognitive linguistics, drawing on the theoretical framework proposed by (Croft & Cruse, 2004). It posits three hypotheses pertaining to cognitive linguistics: (1) Language is not independent of an individual's cognitive processes, (2) Grammar is acquired through conceptual mechanisms, and (3) Language knowledge is a product of language usage. Cognitive linguistics emphasizes the examination of lexical notions. According to Evans and Green (2018) define the lexical notion as the meaning conveyed by a word or lexical form, using standard terminology. "War" and "conflict" can be organized in several configuration at the conceptual level. Merriam-Webster defines the term "war" as a state of openly declared armed confrontation between states or nations. The noun "conflict" refers to a competing or opposed action between incompatible entities, such as divergent ideas, interests, or individuals.

A lexical concept as a conventional semantic unit that possesses a distinct form and represents a specific linguistic unit, such as a word (lemma) (Evans & Green, 2018). Evans also stated a lexical concept is a semantic element that is combined with a phonological vehicle in a symbolic unit (Evans, 2009). Moreover, the lexical concept of the noun "time" is categorized into five distinct categories: duration, moment, event, measurement system, and instance/occurrence (Evans, 2005). This category will be utilized in the analysis of data pertaining to the nouns "war" and "conflict."

In this study, the researchers employ a corpus tools called Sketch Engine to classify the existing data. Consequently, several prior research references assist researchers in effectively processing data and interpreting its implications. Typically, conducting a thorough analysis of an individual word inside a corpus necessitates extensive examination and a substantial amount of corpus data to observe significant outcomes. Previous research conducted by Lukin and Maruggo, "War in Law: A Corpus Linguistic Study of the Lexical Item War in the Laws of War" has demonstrated the utility of the term "war" within the framework of the law of war, particularly in its linguistic application. The research provides significant insights into the portrayal, definition, and use of "war" in various legal frameworks and laws that regulate armed conflict. Prior research has demonstrated that the terms "war" and "violence" possess distinct connotations and interpretations within specific contexts. These two words also reflect different ideologies. (Lukin & Marrugo, 2023).

The subsequent research by Citraresmana et al.(2022) examined the lexical concept of Covid-19 through semantic representation within a corpus from 20 distinct English countries. The significance of Citraresmana et al. (2022) study to the researchers' investigation pertains to the identification of lexical concepts through Lexical Concept and Cognitive Models (LCCM) theory, supplemented by semantic representations utilizing open-class vehicle and closed-class vehicle analysis.

Moreover, the previous research, titled "Lexical Means of Verbalization of the English Concept "War" (Khairulina, 2024) demonstrates that the societal perspective on war is consistently influenced and reflected by contemporary media, such as digital platforms, television, and films. Literature and media contribute to a nuanced comprehension of the impacts of war, both historically and in the present day. The previous study broadly examined the lexical term "war," whereas the current research offers a detailed analysis of the lexical concepts of the nouns "war" and "conflict," utilizing cognitive linguistic theory, based on news coverage of the Israel-Palestine situation from the BBC news channel in 2023. Additionally, the researchers explores how the social conditions in Israel-Palestine are influenced by the writing style of the BBC news channel from England.

1.1. Cognitive Linguistics

Cognitive linguistics is a linguistic field that specifically examines the influence of language on human cognitive processes and how humans perceive and understand the environment. Humans are creatures with souls that organically shape their experiences, which is manifested in their language. Humans are also not merely biological organisms; they also possess cultural and social identities, which are manifested through language.

1.2. Thematic Roles

In this paper, researchers use thematic roles to analyze data to help find lexical concepts. This thematic roles play a role in analyzing semantic and syntactic structures that determine the relationship between entities. The researchers examined how to the representation of sentences in the BBC news channel specifically about the news of Israel vs Palestine in 2023 is dissected using; agent, patient, theme, experiencer, beneficiary, instrument, location, goal, source and stimulus as in the theory (Saeed, 2016).

Certain authors; Gulstad et al., Ravin & Jackendoff propose that agent constitutes a specific subtype of the boarder thematic role known as actor, wherein actor denotes the participant that executes, influences, initiates, or governs the scenario indicated the predicate (Gulstad et al., 1986). Every agent is an actor, but not vice versa. In some cases, an agent is often the subject of the sentence, but not always. Thematic roles are frequently associated with grammatical functions, however they are not synonymous (Ravin & Jackendoff, 1992)

1.3. LCCM (Lexical Concept and Cognitive Models)

The LCCM theory examines the intricacy of semantic units and lexical concepts in language structures, which have a crucial impact on language comprehension (Evans, 2010). However, to gain a more profound comprehension, this theory also considers the underlying cognition, namely the cognitive processes that take place beyond conscious awareness, such as automatic processing and implicit learning. Thus, the entire and holistic processing of language in the human mind may be observed. The LCCM theory helps researchers to determine the lexical concept in understanding the context. However, the concept of individual words cannot be interpreted without the intertwining of another word that is connected.

As written in the previous research (Citraresmana et al., 2022), there is a structure of symbolic units that can help the researchers to examine the lexical concept using vehicle. Evans examines the configuration of symbolic units according to Croft and Cruse (2004) aforementioned concept.

a. Vehicle: "France". Lexical concept: [FRANCE].

b. Vehicle: "NP kick FINITE the bucket." Lexical concept: [AN ANIMATE ENTITIES DIES]

c. Vehicle: "NP FINITE VERB NP NP." Lexical concept: [THING X CAUSES THING Y TO RECEIVE THING Z]. (Evans, 2009)

Evans introduced the Lexical Concept Cognitive Model (LCCM theory) as a symbolic unit. This LCCM serves as the representation type utilized to populate the linguistic system. Evans asserts that a symbolic unit is bipolar configuration of phonological content conveyed by a vehicle. Consequently, the lexical concept constitutes the semantic structure, whereas the vehicle in phonetically manifest (Evans, 2009).

The lexical concept comprises paired closed-class items and paired open-class items. The paired closed-class vehicles encode linguistic content and serve as access points to conceptual knowledge. As a result, the cognitive model presented by Evans is deemed the suitable theory for data analysis.

On the other hand, the term "time" can be perceived as a linear progression, a circular cycle, or a more intricate entity, contingent upon the context and its use. Evans classifies the lexical concept of the term "time" into five separate groups: duration, moment, event, measurement system, and instance/occurrence (Evans, 2005).

Lexical concept of duration refers to the length of time that something lasts or continues. Two variations of the concept of duration correspond to two different subjective experiences. The first phenomenon is referred to as extended duration and pertains to the perception that time is passing at a slower pace than normal. For example: "In the wake of the 1948-49 war, Gaza was occupied by Egypt for 19 years". Egypt's involvement in Gaza spans a specified timeframe of 19 years.

Lexical concept of moment refers to temporal perception which is the capacity to evaluate time concerning distinct intervals. For instance: "Israel losing global support over Gaza bombing." Israel has diminished its global

reputation due to its prolonged and brutal assaults on Palestine. In this scenario, time is understood not as an interval with a measurable duration, but rather as a distinct point.

Lexical concept of event demonstrates an instance or occurrence of some nature. For example: "Israel will continue the war against Hamas, with or without international support." The lexical concept of an event can be seen as a temporal experience.

Lexical concept of measurement system shows a fundamental cognitive category that is conceptualized and articulated through language in diverse manners. For example: "The word "Pallywood" consistently peaked at either 9,500 or 13,000 mentions in a single month on X". The numbers 9,500 or 13,000 represent the precise nominal value that may constitute one of components of the measurement system.

Lexical concept of instance is based on the idea that temporal events may be counted, which means that different events can be seen as instances or examples of the 'same' event. For instance: "However, as previous Israeli wars show, calls for a ceasefire will soon become too loud to be ignored." The term 'previous' indicates a prior Israeli conflict, and the future tense 'will' implies a consequential event in the future.

2. Method

The study included a qualitative research method. All data were acquired using corpus tool by measuring the frequency and word occurrence. This aligns with the principles of Corpus Linguistics, which involves the qualitative analysis patterns and frequency of language usage. According to McEnery and Wilson, Corpus Linguistics also more often analyzes the methodology than analyzes the language aspects which need explanation and description (McEnery & Wilson, 2001). The researchers used Sketch Engine, to conduct a comprehensive search for all nouns of "war" and "conflict" in 25 articles on the BBC channel specifically addressing the news of Israel vs Palestine in 2023. Subsequently, the researchers scrutinized the significance that arose from examining the collocation of the two terms. One strategy employed in this study aligns with Creswell's theory use of phenomenology, which aims to elucidate the collective interpretation of individuals regarding their diverse life experiences pertaining to concepts or phenomena (Creswell, 2003). The objective is to condense individual encounters with events into depictions of universal essences or fundamental elements. This method is employed based on the cognitive process of people in forming conceptions, which is influenced by the description of the Israel-Palestine conflict as portrayed on the BBC 2023 channel. Cognitive linguistics research uses corpus methodologies to investigate the interpretation of human language, thinking, and perception. Corpus analysis helps in identifying cognitive patterns by examining the linguistic structure and semantic significance of a word.

Qualitative research seeks to comprehend the significance of events and human interactions within specific contexts. Furthermore, the researchers examined the linguistic components of language in connection to other linguistic components, such as in the distributional technique (Zaim, 2018). Finally, the researchers observed the development of lexical concepts and documented the observed patterns based on the cognitive structure of language and the semantic content of words.

3. Results

According to the conducted study, in 2023, there were a total of 37,011 tokens extracted from 25 news articles on the BBC Channel discussing the topic of Israel vs Palestine. In addition, this corpus contained a total of 32,022 word types. Among these tokens and word types, the frequency of "war" as a noun appeared 267 times ($F=267$), while the noun "conflict" appeared 75 times ($F=75$). It shows a notable disparity in the usage of the words "war" and "conflict." Afterward, the researchers examine the most prominent collocations in both noun categories, yielding a total of 10 collocations to delve deeper into the interplay between each word.

Table 1: 10 top collocations of “war” as a noun in Sketch Engine

Word	Grammatical relation	Count	Word	Grammatical relation	Count
1 Israel-Gaza	modifiers of "war"	56	6 continue	verbs with "war" as object	10
2 Gaza noun	modifiers of "war"	35	7 draw	... to "war"	9
3 follow	verbs with "war" as subject	13	8 remain	verbs with "war" as object	9
4 more adjective	... on "war"	13	9 different	adjective predicates of "war"	8
5 Israel noun	modifiers of "war"	24	10 Hezbollah	"war" with ...	9

Table 2: 10 top collocations of “conflict” as a noun in Sketch Engine

Word ↓	Grammatical relation	Count	Word	Grammatical relation	Count
1 explain	verbs with "conflict" as subject	12	6 Israel-Palestinian	modifiers of "conflict"	3
2 history	... of "conflict"	12	7 century	... of "conflict"	2
3 something	"conflict" into ...	9	8 other	modifiers of "conflict"	2
4 turn	verbs with "conflict" as object	9	9 worldwide	modifiers of "conflict"	1
5 current	modifiers of "conflict"	3	10 Israeli-Palestinian	modifiers of "conflict"	1

Based on the table provided, it can be inferred that there are collocations associated with the term “war”, such as; *Israel-Gaza*, *Gaza*, *follow*, *more*, *Israel*, *continue*, *draw*, *remain*, *different*, and *Hezbollah*. In the context of the noun conflict, there are precise collocations, particularly; *explain*, *history*, *something*, *turn*, *current*, *Israel-Palestinian*, *century*, *other*, *worldwide*, and *Israeli-Palestinian*. The researchers determine the lexical concept by examining the concordance of the nouns “war” and “conflict” when they are paired with highly collocation words, and observing how these combinations generate a certain concept. Alongside examining the predominant collocations of the nouns war and conflict, researchers analyzed the near-synonyms for these terms utilizing news data regarding Israel vs Palestine from the BBC news channel in 2023. The methods for identifying near-synonyms by assessing word significance through Merriam-Webster online dictionary. The term “war” contains near-synonyms including; *conflict*, *fighting*, *battle*, *violence*, and *hostility*. Meanwhile, the term conflict has near-synonyms with *war* and *schism*. Upon examining near-synonyms in Merriam-Webster (online dictionary), it may be concluded that “war” and “conflict” are synonyms, however their meanings may alter based on contextual usage.

According to Evans, lexical concept is the meaning that is represented by a lexical form or word. Examples of temporal expressions from English include the words *time*, *past*, *present*, and *future*, among others. The lexical concepts that underlie words of this kind can be organized in several ways at the conceptual level (Evans, 2005). Following that, the researchers examined the lexical concept employing sentences in the corpus tools (Sketch Engine) which were selected based on the top collocation. The sentence feature is a robust tool that enables users to search for particular words or phrases inside a corpus and examine the surrounding context. Since no lexical concept can be generated from a single word, the sentence can assemble itself into a lexical concept structure. Data that underwent additional analysis are summarized below:

Table 3: Sentences that construct the lexical concept of ‘war’ using collocation.

No	Noun	Collocation	Collocation Frequency	Sentence
1	War	Israel-Gaza	56	Israel-Gaza war : Half of Gaza's population is starving, as fighting there continues.
2		Gaza	35	London and Jerusalem Reuters Israeli troops prepared to enter Gaza on Wednesday, when intense fighting continued across the territory Israel's foreign minister has said it will continue the war in Gaza "with or without international support".
3		Continue	10	The day after the General Assembly vote and President Biden's warning, Eli Cohen told a visiting diplomat: "Israel will continue the war against Hamas, with or without international support."

Table 4: Sentences that construct the lexical concept of 'war' using near-synonym.

No	Noun	Near-Synonym of War	Near-Synonym Frequency	Sentence
1	War	Conflict	75	The longer the war in Gaza goes on, and as Israel kills more Palestinian civilians and destroys tens of thousands of homes, the greater the risk of conflict involving some members of those two camps.
2		Fighting	18	Mark Lowen: Israel may be fighting in Gaza, but fear remains a war with Hezbollah could turn the conflict into something even deadlier.
3		Battle	13	The Israel-Gaza battles raging on social media.
4		Violence	11	Palestinians under attack as Israeli settler violence surges.
5		Hostility	5	The UN says 1.9 million Palestinians have fled their homes since the war began. So far, the US has supported Israel's opposition to a pause in hostilities .

Table 5: Sentences that construct the lexical concept of 'conflict' using collocation.

No	Noun	Collocation	Collocation Frequency	Sentence
1	Conflict	Explained	12	Israel Gaza war: History of the conflict explained , The Palestinian militant group Hamas launched an unprecedented assault on Israel on 7 October, with hundreds of gunmen infiltrating communities near the Gaza Strip.
2		Turn	9	Mark Lowen: Israel may be fighting in Gaza, but fear remains a war with Hezbollah could turn the conflict into something even deadlier.
3		Current	3	Women and children make up about 70% of those who have been killed in Gaza during the current conflict , says the Hamas-run health ministry.

Table 6: Sentences that construct the lexical concept of 'conflict' using near-synonym.

No	Noun	Near-Synonym of Conflict	Near-Synonym Frequency	Sentence
1	Conflict	War	267	Will the war in Gaza shock Israelis and Palestinians into ending their century of conflict over the land between the Mediterranean Sea and the Jordan river?
2		Schism	1	These are just two examples - viewed millions of times each - showcasing the social media schism in the Israel-Gaza war that has brought denial of atrocities and human suffering to the forefront of online debate about the conflict.

4. Discussion

In this section, the researchers agree with Evans (2009), which posits that the development of lexical concepts relies on an intricate process that is closely intertwined with sentence structure and its contextual associations. Evans (2005) shows that the lexical concept of time may also be applied to the nouns war and conflict. However, the researchers discovered that the lexical concept is not limited to 5 conventional categories. This demonstrates that the writing style used in BBC Channel 2023 generated a lexical concept that symbolizes the terms “war” and “conflict.” This is because language is arbitrary and constructed based on human cognitive processes. Besides, the sociocultural context during the time of writing this BBC news article in 2023 may have significantly impacted the political stance of the UK and its historical relationship with Israel and Palestine.

In this setting, the formation of lexical concepts was shaped by the occurrence of “war” and “conflict,” which exhibited significant disparities. The frequency of war in 25 news articles concerning Israel vs Palestine is approximately 3.6 times higher than the frequency of conflict. Although both nouns may appear similar, they possess distinct meanings and exert diverse impacts in the realm of news. Furthermore, the terms war and conflict have negative connotations due to their protracted negative consequences. This issue has persisted for centuries, with sporadic periods that have yet to deliver an end to it. These two words encapsulate the ongoing dispute and tension between Israel vs Palestine, particularly in 2023 forward. As long as this continues, their descendants will continue to know each other’s country in a manner other than as enemies who are at war with each other.

4.1 The Lexical Concept of “War” as an Event

Future Tenses

- (1) London and Jerusalem Reuters Israeli troops prepared to enter Gaza on Wednesday, when intense fighting continued across the territory Israel's foreign minister has said it will **continue** the war in Gaza "with or without international support".
- (2) The day after the General Assembly vote and President Biden's warning, Eli Cohen told a visiting diplomat: "Israel will **continue** the war against Hamas, with or without international support."

Table 7: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “continue”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (will continue)	Designates an entity as an event that will happen in the future and the evidence-based on formal statement
Lexical class: determiner (the)	Designates to particular things, people, places
Lexical class: noun (It; Israel)	Designates an entity as an object (as one possibility)
Grammatical relation: subject (It; Israel)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (war)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Active voice: through the verb form	Point of view being situated at the agent
Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer

Table 8: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “continue”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
It	Proper place

Israel	Proper place
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The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “continue” shows [ANNOUNCEMENT OF EVENT]. The war can be interpreted as an event concept that aligns with Evans (2005). In 2023, the Israeli military continued its offensive operations, with one particularly severe incident involving the bombing of a hospital. A significant number of youngsters perished. According to United Nations OCHA figures, the overall number of Palestinian fatalities in 2023 was 13,950, with 550 deaths and 13,400 injuries. In contrast, the number of Israeli nationals who lost their lives was far lower, with 287 fatalities, including 37 deaths and 250 injuries. The comparison between Israeli and Palestinian fatalities reveals a significant disparity, with Israeli casualties accounting for only 2.06% of the total Palestinian casualties. This discrepancy raises concerns about the possibility of Israel engaging in genocidal actions against Palestine. To conclude, the semantic representation revealed from the lexical concept is [N/NP1 (the authorized country) will continue (attack incident) N/NP2 (information assertion)].

4.2 The Lexical Concept of “War” as an Action

Present Tenses

- (3) Israel-Gaza war : Half of Gaza's population is starving, as fighting there **continues**.
- (4) The longer the war in Gaza **goes on**, and as Israel **kills** more Palestinian civilians and **destroys** tens of thousands of homes, the greater the risk of conflict involving some members of those two camps.
- (5) Mark Lowen: Israel may be fighting in Gaza, but fear **remains** a war with Hezbollah **could turn** the conflict into something even deadlier.
- (6) Palestinians under attack as Israeli settler violence **surges**.
- (7) The UN **says** 1.9 million Palestinians have fled their homes since the war began.

Table 9: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb]”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (continues, goes on, kills, destroys, remains, could turn, surges, says)	Designates an entity as an action/activity executed continuously
Grammatical relation: subject (Israel-Gaza; War in Gaza; Israel, Israeli, The UN)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (fighting, war, conflict, violence)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Active voice: through the verb form	Point of view being situated at the agent
Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer

Table 10: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb]”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Israel-Gaza	Proper nouns to designate the specific area
War in Gaza	A proper name refers to armed conflict that happens in Gaza
Israel	Proper place
Israeli	A proper name functions as a collective noun referring to the people who have the authority

The UN	Proper name functions as a collective noun referring to people who conduct the rules around the world
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The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb]” shows [INFORMATIONAL ACTION]. In this instance, the researchers incorporated a lexical concept category as an action to enhance Evans’s (2005) thought process. The noun “war” can denote an atypical action. According to the BBC news report, those sentences demonstrate ongoing offensive operations. Agent does actions that demonstrate the verbs of destruction and aggression towards other entities, resulting in casualties. To conclude, the semantic representation revealed from the lexical concept is [N/NP1 (topics) verb (attacking action) N/NP2 (accurate information)].

Present Continuous Tense

(8) The Israel-Gaza battles **raging** on social media.

Table 11: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb+ing]”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (raging)	Designates an entity as an action/activity executed continuously
Lexical class: prep (on)	Designates something in contact with an outer surface
Grammatical relation: subject (The Israel-Gaza battles)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (social media)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Active voice: through the verb form	Point of view being situated at the agent
Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer

Table 12: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb+ing]”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
The Israel-Gaza	Proper nouns to designate the specific area

The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “near synonym war + [verb+ing]” shows [INFORMATIONAL ACTION]. In this example above, the information that has been written can be interpreted as a fact. The statement constitutes headline news, resulting in the omission of the auxiliary verb (are); nonetheless, it retains a present tense categorization while conveying a negative connotation, specifically through term “raging”, which must be accompanied by auxiliary verb “are”. To conclude, the semantic representation revealed from the lexical concept is [N/NP1 (specific area) verb (informational action) N/NP2 (informational assertion)]. The researchers integrated a lexical concept category as an action to augment the cognitive framework proposed by Evans (2005). The noun war can signify an active action.

4.3 The Lexical Concept of “Conflict” as an Event

Passive Sentence

- (9) Israel Gaza war: History of the **conflict explained**, The Palestinian militant group Hamas launched an unprecedented assault on Israel on 7 October, with hundreds of gunmen infiltrating communities near the Gaza Strip.

Table 13: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “explained”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (explained)	Designates an entity as an event that happened in the past; this entity proved true and was approved officially by formal agreement.
Lexical class: noun phrase (Israel-Gaza war)	Designates to describe the entity as modified by adjective
Lexical class: prep (of)	Designates an entity’s possession or belonging
Grammatical relation: subject (Israel-Gaza war)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (conflict)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Passive voice: through the verb form	Designates entities occurred not from the point of view of the agent
Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer

Table 14: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “explained”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Israel-Gaza	Proper nouns to designate the specific area

The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “explained” shows [AGENTLESS INFORMATIONAL ASSERTION]. The information occurred not from the point of view of the agent. The contrary event transpired as illustrated in other media, which portrayed the Palestinian people who are attacking Israel rather than the reverse, hence necessitating a passive construction to convey the historical context that instigated the conflict. The researchers agree with Evans (2005) regarding the lexical concept of “time” that can be applied in “conflict” as an event. The statement constitutes headline news, resulting in the omission of the auxiliary verb (is); nonetheless, it retains a present tense categorization. To conclude, the semantic representation of vehicles “explained” in passive voice is [N/NP1 (topic) explained (formal evidence) CLAUSE PHRASE] the writers did not insert the agent involved.

4.4 The Lexical Concept of “Conflict” as an Action

Present Tense

- (10) Women and children **make up** about 70% of those who have been killed in Gaza during the current conflict, says the Hamas-run health ministry.
- (11) These **are** just two examples - viewed millions of times each - showcasing the social media schism in the Israel-Gaza war that has brought denial of atrocities and human suffering to the forefront of online debate about the conflict.

Table 15: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “[verb] + conflict”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (make up, are)	Designates an entity as an action/activity executed continuously
Lexical class: prep (about)	Designates to describe the entity as a reasonably close to
Grammatical relation: subject (women and children; these)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (70%; examples)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Active voice: through the verb form	Point of view being situated at the agent
Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer

Table 16: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “[verb] + conflict”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Women and children	Designates the adult female people (women); a son or daughter of human parents (children)
These	Designates the entity as a plural form of this

The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “[verb] + conflict” shows [INFORMATIONAL ACTION]. The assault resulted in the casualties of women and children who contravened international warfare regulations. The data indicated that 70% of the victims were Palestinians. The controversy surrounding the news of Israel-Gaza incited an extensive debate on social media, encompassing both advantages and disadvantages. The data reveals an additional lexical concept of action, complementing the perspectives of Evans (2005), due to the actions undertaken by one party that resulted in loss of life and incited turmoil on social media, despite the widespread condemnation of the Israeli attack on Palestine. To conclude, the semantic representation revealed from the lexical concept is [N/NP1 (foreground information) verb (action) conflict N/NP2 (additional information)].

Future Tense

- (12) **Will** the war in Gaza **shock** Israelis and Palestinians into ending their century of conflict over the land between the Mediterranean Sea and the Jordan river?

Table 17: Schematic content associated with closed-class vehicles “[will] [shock] + conflict”

Closed class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
Lexical class: verb (shock)	Designates an entity that causes such disturbance suddenly
Lexical class: determiner (the)	Designates to particular things, people, places
Lexical class: prep (in)	Designates entity is inside a container, place, or area
Grammatical relation: subject (war in Gaza)	Designates entity being the primary or focal entity in a designated relationship
Grammatical relation: object (Israelis and Palestinians)	The secondary entity in a designated relationship
Active voice: through the verb form	Point of view being situated at the agent

Declarative word order	Speakers know the situation is to be true and assert it to the hearer
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Table 18: Rich content associated with open-class vehicles “[will] [shock] + conflict”

Open-class vehicles	Schematic semantic content
War in Gaza	A proper name refers to armed conflict that happens in Gaza

The schematic content associated with the closed class and rich content associated with open class vehicles “[will] [shock] + conflict” shows [POTENTIAL RESULT]. The lexical concept shows the semantic representation [Will N/NP1 (topic) shock (action) conflict N/NP2 (the authorized countries)]. Conflict can be defined as an act of aggression that incites discord that enhances the framework Evans’s theory (2005).

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the data analysis indicates that the nouns "war" and "conflict" are categorized as near-synonyms in the Merriam-Webster online dictionary, reflecting the identical lexical concepts of “event” and “action.” This aligns with the perspective of Evans (2005), since the nouns war and conflict denote acts conducted by one entity against another.

Researchers categorize these lexical concepts according to semantic representation, using both closed-class and open-class vehicles, thereby demonstrating how a word’s lexical notion becomes apparent while constructing a sentence. Each sentence contains a visible verb, facilitating researchers’ identification of its lexical concept. Data derived from 25 articles concerning Israel vs Palestine in BBC Channel 2023 indicates that the lexical concept of “war,” associated with the word “continue,” is classified as “an event announcement,” thereby identifying it as an “event.” Furthermore, the exploration of the lexical concept of “war” through near-synonym of using vehicle “verbs” results in “informational action,” which we categorize as an “action”. Simultaneously, the lexical concept of “conflict” which is associated with the word “explained”, is an “agentless informational assertion” that falls into the “event” category. Therefore, the lexical concept of “conflict” alongside near-synonyms with vehicle “verbs” reveals the lexical concepts of “informational action” and “potential result” which are classified under the “action” category.

Social factors significantly impact the coverage of the Israel-Palestine conflict, particularly by BBC channel in 2023. BBC, which is UK-owned and exhibits a discernible bias towards Israel published multiple reports on the alleged manipulation of Palestinian casualties, referred to as Pallywood, while global discourse has condemned Israel’s actions as unjust and disproportionate, leading to the emergence of the term genocide. While both words refer to a state of disagreement, the noun "war" typically conveys a more intense and impactful level of conflict compared to the noun "conflict." The mere use of the phrase war can have significant repercussions and exert a profound influence on multiple nations. Despite the United Nations' intervention, it was unable to halt the unfolding conflict. Within the BBC Channel news, there is a portrayal of Israel's involvement in the war that suggests they may not be wholly at fault. The news highlights the actions of other actors, such as Hamas and Hezbollah, who had previously attacked Israel. Additionally, the participation of Eli Cohen is emphasized, as they publicly express their intention to continue the onslaught on Gaza. However, the international community strongly criticized the large-scale attack on Rafah that occurred on May 7, 2024, when Israel intensified its military operation.

Historically, it is undeniable that England played a significant role in backing the Zionist movement. While the writing in the news aims to maintain neutrality, it does include relevant information regarding the historical context of the ongoing war and the key parties involved in explaining the reasons behind Israel's attack on Gaza. Some remarks prioritize highlighting Israel's military prowess instead of advocating for peace.

According to LCCM theory, researchers discovered that the lexical concepts are constructed from the arrangement of words in sentences. Consequently, it can be concluded that “war” and “conflict” are significantly interconnected particularly in BBC news 2023, as both exhibit the same lexical concept of “event” and “action”. The previous research mostly concentrated on the noun “war” without juxtaposing it with other nouns.

Nevertheless, this study is limited in scope since it solely focuses on comparing the lexical concept of war and conflict nouns, so aiming to uncover the underlying reasons for the observed disparities. Additional research can investigate the lexical concept of genocide and the fundamental ideological disparities between Israel and Palestine.

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